

Challenge Leverage Score: A Decision-Support Framework for MLB Automated Ball-Strike System Challenges

Christopher A. Hamm

Version 0.5 — April 2026

Abstract

The Automated Ball-Strike (ABS) challenge system in Major League Baseball creates a finite-resource decision problem: when is it optimal to challenge a pitch call? Public discussion of ABS challenges has been driven largely by intuition, yet the decision can be formalized as an expected-value problem under resource constraints. I present the Challenge Leverage Score (CLS), a decision-support framework for evaluating the expected value of challenging any given pitch.

The CLS formalizes the challenge decision as an expected-value problem in which the value of overturning a call is weighed against the opportunity cost of spending a finite resource. The framework combines three components: a challenge conservation cost term that approximates the future value of retaining a challenge; an empirical win expectancy table derived from 2020–2026 Statcast data; and an overturn probability model conditioned on pitch location and umpire-specific miss tendencies. The model is partially calibrated using 2026 regular season challenge data and updated incrementally as the season progresses.

I extend the framework with a Bayesian formulation that propagates uncertainty through the win expectancy and umpire tendency components, returning a posterior distribution over CLS values with credible intervals. The umpire tendency component uses a hierarchical Beta-Binomial shrinkage model grouped by umpire, batter handedness, pitcher handedness, batter height, and miss direction. A contextual Bayesian lookup enables situation-specific inference while falling back to aggregate umpire information when context-specific data are sparse.

The framework reveals several consistent patterns. From the batting team’s perspective, challenge leverage peaks at the 3–2 count, where overturning a called strike converts an immediate strikeout into ball four and maximizes the resulting win expectancy swing. Late innings amplify this effect sharply—innings 7 through 9 in close games produce the highest CLS values, with a batting team trailing by one run in the ninth representing the single highest-leverage scenario. This exceeds even a tie game because the need for baserunners is most acute. A runner already on base further increases challenge value by converting a potential strikeout into a walk that forces advancement. Conversely, challenge conservation matters most early in close games, where the future value of retaining a challenge is highest. Blowouts in either direction collapse the conservation cost, and the 3–0 count also produces low leverage despite its superficially favorable count structure. Umpire identity also matters: miss propensity varies across the qualified umpire pool, and spatial miss patterns differ enough that challenge value depends not only on miss distance but also on where a given umpire tends to miss.

The entire framework is implemented as an open-source Python toolkit and is available under a custom license.

1 Introduction

The 2026 Major League Baseball season introduced the Automated Ball-Strike (ABS) system, replacing over a century of human ball-strike adjudication. Under the ABS Challenge System, batters, pitchers, and catchers may challenge any ball or strike call, which is adjudicated against a fixed geometric strike zone. Each team begins with two challenges per game and retains a challenge if their challenge is upheld. As of mid-April 2026, the overturn rate is approximately 56.5% (~900 challenges), indicating that a substantial fraction of edge calls are incorrect.

The ABS challenge is distinct from the traditional replay challenge used for field plays, but both draw from the same two-challenge allotment. A failed field challenge reduces the number of ABS challenges available, and vice versa. This framework addresses only ABS ball-strike decisions, but the conservation cost term explicitly incorporates the number of challenges remaining, so it adjusts naturally when a field challenge has already been used.

Challenges are finite and strategically important, yet discussion of their use has been largely informal and intuition-driven. Challenges are often issued without a clear framework for weighing the cost of expending a challenge against the benefit of altering the count or at-bat outcome. This paper provides a formal framework for that decision.

I present the Challenge Leverage Score (CLS), defined as

$$\text{CLS} = P(O = 1 | x) \cdot \Delta WE - C_s(i, d, r)$$

where $P(O = 1 | x)$ is the probability the call is overturned given pitch context x , ΔWE is the change in win expectancy from overturning the call, and $C_s(i, d, r)$ is the opportunity cost of spending a challenge, where i is the inning, d is the score differential, and r is the number of challenges remaining. CLS is measured in win expectancy units; for example, +0.080 corresponds to an 8 percentage point increase in win probability. A positive CLS indicates that issuing a challenge has positive expected value.

The paper presents the mathematical framework, empirical data pipeline, Bayesian extension, and implementation.

2 Background and Related Work

2.1 Win Expectancy

Win expectancy (WE) is the probability that a team wins given the current game state and has a long history in sabermetrics. Tango et al. (2006) provide foundational WE tables derived from historical play-by-play data, keyed on inning, score differential, outs, and base state. I extend the standard formulation to include count (balls and strikes) and the inning half (top/bottom), which is necessary to account for the home team’s last-at-bat advantage.

2.2 Challenge Systems in Sports

Decision frameworks for challenge systems have been studied in other sports contexts. In tennis, Hawk-Eye challenge strategies have been analyzed as finite-horizon sequential decision problems (Carboch et al., 2014). In American football, the value of coach’s challenges has been studied using dynamic programming (Romer, 2006). To my knowledge, no formal framework has been published for the MLB ABS challenge system.

2.3 Umpire Bias and Framing

A substantial literature documents systematic biases in umpire ball-strike calls (Judge et al., 2010). Pitch framing research has demonstrated that catchers can influence call rates on edge pitches. Studies have documented umpire-specific tendencies on edge calls, controlling for pitch location, batter handedness, and pitcher handedness (Fast, 2010; Deshpande and Wyner, 2017). The umpire tendency model extends this literature by incorporating batter height as an additional grouping dimension.

3 The CLS Framework

The challenge decision in baseball is a finite-resource expected-value problem: a team holds a limited number of challenges, faces uncertainty about whether a call is correct, and must weigh the immediate benefit of overturning the call against the opportunity cost of depleting that resource before a higher-leverage future situation. This structure motivates a formal decomposition of the challenge decision. The CLS framework decomposes the decision into three components: overturn probability, win expectancy change, and challenge conservation cost.

3.1 Overturn Probability

The overturn probability $P(O = 1 | x)$ is modeled using logistic regression:

$$\text{logit}(p) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 m + \beta_2(u - \bar{u}) + \beta_3 b + \beta_4 p_t + \beta_5 c$$

where β_0 is the intercept, x includes pitch-level features such as miss distance, pitch location relative to the strike zone boundary, and contextual batter, pitcher, catcher, and umpire effects. Here, m is the miss distance in inches from the nearest zone edge; u is the umpire miss tendency; $\bar{u} = 0.0977$ is the league mean umpire propensity; b is the batter edge-call tendency; p_t is the pitcher edge-call tendency; and c is the catcher framing effect. The umpire term is mean-centered so that β_0 reflects the overturn probability for a league-average umpire independently of the umpire covariate. All tendency terms operate on the logit scale and combine additively.

Intercept calibration. β_0 was calibrated from early 2026 ABS challenge outcome data ($n \approx 800$ challenges as of 2026-04-09). The observed overturn rate of 56.5% was used to solve for β_0 accounting for the mean predictor values across actual challenged pitches—specifically the mean miss distance of 1.251 inches and the league-average umpire miss propensity of 0.0977. Because the umpire term is mean-centered, it drops out of the calibration equation:

$$\beta_0 = \text{logit}(0.565) - \beta_{\text{miss}} \times 1.251 - \beta_{\text{ump}} \times 0 = -0.1777$$

This replaces the development placeholder of -2.0 . All remaining coefficients ($\beta_{\text{miss}}, \beta_{\text{ump}}, \beta_{\text{batter}}, \beta_{\text{pitcher}}, \beta_{\text{catcher}}$) remain placeholder values pending sufficient pitch-level challenge outcome data to support logistic regression. The calibrated β_0 ensures realistic absolute overturn probabilities while preserving relative orderings driven by pitch location and umpire identity.

3.2 Delta Win Expectancy

Win expectancy $WE(G)$ is the probability that the batting team wins given game state

$$G = (\text{inning}, \text{inning_half}, \text{score_differential}, \text{outs}, \text{balls}, \text{strikes}, \text{base_state}).$$

The value of overturning a call is

$$\Delta WE = WE(G_{\text{overturned}}) - WE(G_{\text{stands}}).$$

where $G_{\text{overturned}}$ is the resulting game state if the call is overturned, and G_{stands} is the resulting game state if the call stands. ΔWE can be negative. For example, if a called ball is actually a strike, overturning the call gives the pitcher a free strike, reducing the batting team’s win expectancy.

Note that ΔWE throughout this framework is defined from the perspective of the batting team: a positive ΔWE means the overturned call helps the team at the plate. To adopt the defensive team’s perspective, reverse the sign. A challenge that is clearly worth making for the batting team represents an equal opportunity for the pitching team—if the pitching team could challenge the same call, the CLS magnitude represents their expected gain from doing so.

The win expectancy table is built from 2020–2026 Statcast called pitch data using the `bat_win_exp` field, which represents the batting team’s win expectancy before each pitch as computed by MLB using all pitch outcomes. Beta-Binomial shrinkage with tuned prior $\alpha = \beta = 2$ is applied to handle sparse game states.

To validate the constructed win expectancy table (Table 1), representative game states are compared against the benchmark values reported in Tango et al. (2006).

Table 1: Win expectancy replication against Tango et al. (2006). Diff = Ours – Tango. ▲ = sparse cell ($n < 20$).

Description	Tango	Mine	Diff	n	
Bot 9, home down 1, 2 outs, bases empty	0.042	0.051	+0.009	495	
Bot 9, home down 1, 0 outs, bases empty	0.194	0.205	+0.011	929	
Bot 9, home down 1, 0 outs, bases loaded	0.739	0.669	-0.070	11	▲
Bot 9, tied, 0 outs, bases empty	0.634	0.638	+0.004	932	
Bot 9, tied, 2 outs, bases loaded	0.662	0.652	-0.010	48	
Top 9, away up 1, 2 outs, bases empty	0.814	0.804	-0.010	490	
Top 9, away down 1, 0 outs, bases empty	0.159	0.166	+0.007	1,005	
Top 9, tied, 0 outs, bases empty	0.500	0.500	+0.000	1,007	
Bot 8, home down 1, 2 outs, bases empty	0.187	0.199	+0.012	550	
Bot 8, home up 1, 0 outs, bases empty	0.871	0.866	-0.005	997	
Bot 8, tied, 0 outs, bases empty	0.604	0.608	+0.004	1,089	
Top 8, away down 1, 2 outs, bases empty	0.153	0.162	+0.009	559	
Top 8, away up 1, 0 outs, bases empty	0.754	0.744	-0.010	1,059	

The results show close agreement across well-sampled game states, with larger deviations occurring only in sparse situations where sample size is limited. The largest deviation occurs in a sparse bases-loaded state ($n = 11$), where the estimate is expected to be unstable despite shrinkage.

3.3 Challenge Conservation Cost

Challenges are a finite resource. The opportunity cost of spending a challenge now is the value it might have provided in a future higher-leverage situation. I approximate this as

$$C_s(i, d, r) = \lambda_0 \cdot \frac{9 - i}{9} \cdot e^{-k|d|} \cdot \frac{1}{r}.$$

where $\lambda_0 = 0.015$ is a baseline cost scale parameter, $(9 - i)/9$ is the inning factor which decreases linearly as fewer innings remain, $e^{-k|d|}$ is the closeness factor which decays exponentially in blowouts

where saved challenges have little value, and $1/r$ is the challenge factor reflecting that the last remaining challenge is worth more than the first. This formulation approximates the future value of retaining a challenge by decreasing the conservation cost as the number of remaining opportunities declines (via inning), as the game becomes less competitive (via score differential), and as more challenges remain available.

In extra innings, the conservation cost is reduced to a small constant fraction (0.05) because each team receives a fresh challenge at the start of every inning, reducing the value of deferring use.

4 Umpire Tendency Model

The CLS framework requires an estimate of how likely a given umpire is to have called a specific pitch incorrectly. Human umpires are not interchangeable: empirical research has shown that call tendencies differ systematically by umpire identity, pitch location, batter handedness, and pitch context (Judge et al., 2010; Deshpande and Wyner, 2017). The umpire tendency component constructs a shrinkage-adjusted, contextually stratified rate estimate for each active umpire.

4.1 Beta-Binomial Shrinkage Model

For each umpire, I compute the shrinkage-adjusted miss rate grouped by umpire, batter handedness, pitcher handedness, pitch type, Statcast zone, miss direction (high, low, inside, outside), miss favor (pitcher or batter), and batter height bin. Batter height is approximated by the effective zone height ($sz_top - sz_bot$): short (< 1.8 ft), average (1.8–2.0 ft), tall (> 2.0 ft).

The shrinkage estimator is

$$\hat{p}_j = \frac{Y_j + \alpha}{n_j + \alpha + \beta}$$

where Y_j is the number of misses observed in grouping cell j , and n_j is the total number of pitches in that cell. The prior parameters are $\alpha = 2$, $\beta = 20$, corresponding to a prior miss rate of approximately 9%. The asymmetric prior reflects that most edge calls are correct. Umpires with large samples can deviate substantially from the prior; call-up umpires are shrunk toward it.

4.2 Umpire Covariate Centering

The umpire miss propensity term in the linear predictor is mean-centered on the league average ($\bar{u} = 0.0977$):

$$\text{logit}(p) = \beta_0 + \beta_{\text{miss}} \cdot \text{miss_distance} + \beta_{\text{ump}} \cdot (u - \bar{u}) + \dots$$

This centering decouples the intercept calibration from the umpire differentiation term. Without centering, adjusting β_0 to match the observed overturn rate simultaneously shifts all umpires uniformly on the sigmoid, compressing their relative spread. With centering, β_0 reflects the overturn probability for a league-average umpire, and individual umpire deviations above and below that baseline are preserved. The same centering is applied in the Bayesian model’s linear predictor using a fixed league-average constant.

4.3 Regression Model

A logistic regression model with L2-regularized umpire fixed effects is fitted on edge pitches (within 3.0 inches of the strike zone boundary). Predictors include miss distance, miss direction, batter handedness, pitcher handedness, pitch side, pitch type, and batter height bin. L2 regularization

on umpire indicators approximates random-effects shrinkage. This model is used to derive a scalar umpire propensity for the point-estimate CLS.

4.4 Bayesian Hierarchical Umpire Lookup

For the Bayesian CLS model, a hierarchical lookup is used. Given a specific pitch context (umpire, miss direction, batter height bin, batter handedness, pitcher handedness), the model checks whether at least 15 pitches have been observed in that exact context. If so, the Beta posterior is computed from those observations, capturing the umpire’s context-specific tendency. If fewer than 15 pitches are available, the model falls back to the aggregate umpire posterior across all contexts.

This two-level hierarchy enables situation-specific inference while maintaining stability under data sparsity.

5 Bayesian Extension

5.1 Motivation

The point-estimate CLS returns a single value and an implied decision rule. This ignores two sources of uncertainty: (1) many game states have sparse observations in the win expectancy table, so a state with $n = 5$ observations has substantially greater uncertainty than one with $n = 1,000$; and (2) the umpire miss propensity is estimated from data and is not known with certainty. A Bayesian formulation propagates both sources of uncertainty through the CLS calculation.

The practical consequence is that two identical pitches in nominally identical game states can produce materially different credible intervals depending on how frequently that specific game state has been observed historically. A 3–2 count, tie game, bottom of the 9th, bases empty is observed thousands of times, producing a tight posterior for win expectancy and a narrow credible interval for CLS. In contrast, rare game states with limited historical observations produce diffuse posteriors and wider credible intervals, reflecting reduced confidence in the resulting evaluation.

5.2 Model

Three stochastic nodes are modeled as Beta distributions:

$$\begin{aligned} WE_{\text{stands}} &\sim \text{Beta}(\alpha_{\text{stands}}, \beta_{\text{stands}}) \\ WE_{\text{overturned}} &\sim \text{Beta}(\alpha_{\text{over}}, \beta_{\text{over}}) \\ u &\sim \text{Beta}(\alpha_{\text{ump}}, \beta_{\text{ump}}) \end{aligned}$$

Three deterministic quantities are then derived:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta WE &= WE_{\text{overturned}} - WE_{\text{stands}} \\ p_{\text{overturn}} &= \text{sigmoid}(\beta_0 + \beta_{\text{miss}} \cdot \text{miss_dist} + \beta_{\text{ump}} \cdot (u - 0.0977) + \dots) \\ CLS &= p_{\text{overturn}} \cdot \Delta WE - C_s \end{aligned}$$

The Beta posterior parameters for each win expectancy node are derived using the Beta-Binomial conjugate update:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_{\text{post}} &= \alpha_{\text{prior}} + n \cdot \mu_{\text{raw}} \\ \beta_{\text{post}} &= \beta_{\text{prior}} + n \cdot (1 - \mu_{\text{raw}}) \end{aligned}$$

where $\alpha_{\text{prior}} = 2$ and $\beta_{\text{prior}} = 2$, n is the number of observed pitches in that game state, and μ_{raw} is the mean `bat_win_exp` across those observations. The conservation cost C_s is treated as fixed given the game state.

5.3 Inference

Posterior sampling was performed using PyMC with the No-U-Turn Sampler (NUTS), drawing 4,000 samples per chain across 4 chains (16,000 total), with 1,000 warmup steps per chain. Inference is based on the posterior distribution of CLS, and decisions can be evaluated using the posterior probability that $CLS > 0$.

Convergence diagnostics were evaluated using Gelman–Rubin \hat{R} statistics and effective sample size (ESS) metrics following standard Bayesian workflow guidance (McElreath, 2020). All parameters achieved $\hat{R} = 1.00$, with bulk effective sample sizes exceeding 22,000 and tail effective sample sizes exceeding 12,000. No divergent transitions were observed during sampling. These results indicate excellent chain mixing, negligible autocorrelation, and stable posterior estimation.

The diagnostic summary for a representative run is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Posterior convergence diagnostics for a representative Bayesian CLS run. All parameters achieve $\hat{R} = 1.00$ with large effective sample sizes and zero divergences, indicating excellent chain mixing and stable posterior estimation.

Parameter	Mean	SD	ESS (bulk)	ESS (tail)	\hat{R}
WE_{stands}	0.353	0.124	22,336	12,381	1.00
$WE_{\text{overturnd}}$	0.412	0.162	21,902	13,001	1.00
u	0.126	0.009	22,793	12,274	1.00
ΔWE	0.059	0.203	23,324	12,374	1.00
$p_{\text{overturnd}}$	0.847	0.001	22,793	12,274	1.00
CLS	0.050	0.172	23,328	12,349	1.00

6 Data

6.1 Statcast Called Pitch Data

I use the `pybaseball` Python package to pull all called strikes and balls from Baseball Savant for the 2020–2026 seasons (> 2.8 million pitches). For each pitch I retained: game state (inning, score, outs, count, base state), pitch location (`plate_x`, `plate_z`, `sz_top`, `sz_bot`, `zone`), batter and pitcher handedness, and `bat_win_exp` (the batting team’s WE before the pitch as computed by MLB).

The Statcast umpire field was null for all rows queried, so umpire identities were sourced from the MLB Stats API boxscore endpoint and joined to the pitch data on `game_pk`.

6.2 Active Umpires

I defined active umpires as those who worked a game in the 2026 season as determined from umpire assignment records, and those individuals must have called at least 1,000 total pitches in MLB. As of early April 2026, ~80 umpires meet this criterion. The umpire tendency model is built from all 2020–2026 data.

6.3 ABS Challenge Outcome Data

Pitch-level ABS challenge outcome data are sourced from the MLB Stats API play-by-play endpoint, which contains a `reviewDetails` block on challenged pitches. ABS challenges are identified by filtering play events to `isPitch == True`, presence of `reviewDetails`, and call code in `{C, B}` (called strike or called ball only). This filter correctly excludes foul/fair appeals, checked-swing appeals, and other non-ABS review events.

As of 2026-04-14, approximately 900 challenges have been recorded across 2026 regular season games, with an observed overturn rate of $\sim 56\%$. The mean miss distance of challenged pitches is 1.251 inches. These values are used to calibrate the intercept β_0 as described in Section 3.1. Full coefficient estimation requires continued data collection across the season and will be updated at regular intervals once sufficient observations have been made.

7 Validation

7.1 Win Expectancy Table

I validate the WE table against published values from Tango et al. (2006) for a sample of high-density game states. All dense states ($n > 400$) match Tango’s published values within 0.012. One sparse state (bottom of 9th, home down 1, 0 outs, bases loaded, $n = 11$) shows a larger difference of 0.070, attributed to prior shrinkage rather than a data error.

I compare the effect of the Beta-Binomial prior hyperparameters (Table 3). The tuned prior ($\alpha = \beta = 2$) produces substantially less shrinkage on sparse states while leaving dense states unchanged.

Table 3: Win expectancy prior comparison across spot-check states. Shift = shrinkage estimate – Raw WE. Tango values from tangotiger.net/welist.html.

State	n	Raw WE	Default (5,5)	Tuned (2,2)	Tango	Shift (5,5)	Shift (2,2)
Inn 1, tied, 0 outs, bases empty	7,384	0.548	0.548	0.548	0.500	-0.000	-0.000
Inn 9, down 1, 2 outs, bases empty	495	0.047	0.056	0.051	0.042	+0.009	+0.004
Inn 9, tied, 0 outs, bases empty	932	0.639	0.638	0.638	0.634	-0.001	-0.001
Inn 9, tied, 3-2, bases loaded	1	0.939	0.540	0.588	—	-0.399	-0.351
Inn 9, down 1, 2 outs, 3-2, bases loaded	2	0.339	0.473	0.446	—	+0.134	+0.107

7.2 Umpire Tendency Model

The contextual posterior comparison for a representative 2026 pitch illustrates the value of the hierarchical lookup. The contextual posterior ($n = 1488$ pitches in a specific context) returns a mean miss rate of 12.6%, compared to the umpire’s aggregate miss rate of 9.1%. Despite the large sample size, the contextual posterior remains materially different from the aggregate estimate, indicating that umpire miss tendencies are not uniform across contexts. This example illustrates

the core value of the hierarchical lookup: the aggregate posterior would underestimate the umpire’s tendency in this specific situation by approximately 3.5 percentage points.

8 Results

I present six simulation analyses that characterize the behavior of the CLS model across game situations, miss distances, and umpire tendencies (Fig. 5). All figures reflect the calibrated intercept $\beta_0 = -0.1777$ and the mean-centered umpire covariate. Bayesian figures used 4,000 draws per chain across 4 chains with 92.5% credible intervals. All other beta coefficients remain placeholders; relative orderings are directionally correct but absolute CLS magnitudes should be interpreted accordingly. All Bayesian results presented in this section are supported by well-converged posterior samples, as evidenced by the diagnostics in Table 2.

8.1 CLS by Count

The CLS across all 12 ball-strike counts is shown for a league-average umpire on a 1.5-inch miss in a tied game in the 6th inning with no outs and bases empty (Fig. 1). The left panel shows called strikes (ball called outside the zone); the right panel shows called balls (strike called inside the zone).

The 3–2 called strike produces by far the highest CLS (+0.047), roughly twice the value of any other count. This reflects the asymmetric consequences of a 3–2 count: a called strike made incorrectly on what should be ball four ends the at-bat with a walk, producing a large ΔWE . The 3–2 called ball panel bottoms at -0.052 , confirming that challenging any called ball on a 3–2 count is the worst possible use of a challenge from the batting team’s perspective (note: this is a structural property of the framework, not just an observation from this one figure).

The called ball panel is uniformly negative across all counts. Under the batting-team perspective modeled here, overturning a called ball generally reduces win expectancy, making such challenges negative expected value in nearly all observed contexts.

Figure 1: CLS by ball-strike count for called strikes (left) and called balls (right). Inning 6, tied game, 0 outs, bases empty, 1.5-inch miss, league-average umpire. Green = positive CLS (challenge); red = negative CLS (do not challenge). The called ball panel is uniformly negative, indicating that challenging called balls is never the correct decision in this game state from the batting team’s perspective.

8.2 CLS by Inning and Score Differential

The CLS for a 3–2 called strike is shown across innings 1–9 and score differentials from -3 to $+3$, with 1 out and bases empty against a league-average umpire (Fig. 2). Two clean findings emerge. First, being down 1 run in the late innings produces the highest CLS values: down 1 in the 9th inning ($+0.08$) is the single highest-value challenge situation in this simulation. Second, being up by 1 or 2 runs also produces meaningful CLS values in the late innings—a team up by 1 in the 8th inning should not dismiss a challenge simply because the team is ahead.

The model confirms that large score differentials diminish the value of a challenge (Fig. 2). Being ahead by multiple runs produces consistently lower CLS across all innings, particularly early in the game. In contrast, being behind materially increases the value of a challenge, with the highest CLS values occurring when trailing by one run. This asymmetry reflects the nonlinear impact of game state on win expectancy: marginal gains are more valuable when attempting to close a deficit than when protecting a lead. The first inning consistently shows the lowest CLS values regardless of score differential, reflecting the limited immediate impact of any single call early in the game.

Figure 2: CLS by inning and score differential. 3-2 called strike, 1 out, bases empty, 1.5-inch miss, league-average umpire. The single highest-value challenge situation is down 1 in the 9th inning ($+0.08$). Blowout situations (score differential ± 3) produce substantially lower CLS across all innings.

8.3 Miss Distance Sensitivity (Bayesian)

The Bayesian posterior mean CLS as a function of miss distance from 0.5 to 3.0 inches is shown for five representative game states, using a called strike with one out and the reference umpire Edwin Moscoso (Fig. 3). CLS increases monotonically with miss distance across all game states, reflecting the higher likelihood of overturn for more egregious misses. However, the dominant driver of variation is game state: high-leverage situations (e.g., late innings in tied or one-run

games) exhibit substantially higher CLS across the entire range of miss distances, while low-leverage situations (e.g., early innings) remain near zero even for large miss distances. This demonstrates that miss severity alone is insufficient to justify a challenge; its value is fundamentally mediated by game context.

Figure 3: Bayesian CLS vs miss distance for five game states. Posterior mean (solid line). Reference umpire: Edwin Moscoso. The dashed line at CLS = 0 is the challenge threshold.

8.4 Challenge Conservation Cost

The challenge conservation cost C_s is shown as a function of inning, score differential, and number of challenges remaining (Fig. 4). Three findings stand out. First, the gap between 1 and 2 challenges remaining is largest in tied games in the early innings. In inning 1 with the game tied, the last remaining challenge carries nearly twice the conservation cost of the second-to-last challenge. Second, situations with large score differentials (down 3) flatten the conservation cost to near zero by inning 4. Third, the sharp drop to near-zero at inning 9 followed by a small bump in extra innings is clearly visible, correctly reflecting the ABS rule that each team receives a fresh challenge at the start of every extra inning.

Figure 4: Challenge conservation cost C_s across the game, by score differential and challenges remaining. Solid lines: 1 challenge remaining. Dashed lines: 2 challenges remaining. The vertical dotted line marks the start of extra innings. Conservation cost is highest in tied games early in the game with only one challenge remaining, and approaches zero in blowouts and late innings.

8.5 Umpire Miss Zones

Kernel density estimates of miss call locations are shown for six active umpires (Rob Drake, CB Bucknor, Laz Diaz, Hunter Wendelstedt, Ron Kulpa, and Doug Eddings), filtered to right-handed pitchers against right-handed batters of average height (Fig. 5). The black rectangle is the median strike zone for this height bin.

These six umpires share a striking pattern: their missed calls cluster on the outside-low corner for right-handed batters, as viewed from the catcher’s perspective (i.e., the right side of the zone in Fig. 5). This reflects a systematic bias in how human umpires call the outside corner, consistent with findings in the pitch framing literature (Brooks et al., 2013). The practical implication for the CLS model is direct: when facing any of these six umpires with a right-handed batter, missed calls near the outside-low corner deserve particular scrutiny.

Miss call locations — top 6 miss-prone active umpires
RHB vs RHP, average batter height (2020-2026)

Figure 5: Kernel density estimates of miss call locations for six 2026 umpires. Right-handed batters vs right-handed pitchers, average batter height. The black rectangle is the median strike zone for this height bin. All six umpires show concentrated miss density near the outside-low corner (right side of the zone from the catcher’s view).

8.6 Umpire Miss Rate Rankings

The shrinkage-adjusted miss rate and regression effect for a subset of active 2026 umpires are reported in Table 4. Shrinkage is necessary because many umpire-context cells have limited observations; raw miss rates in such cells are highly variable and can produce extreme estimates. The Beta-Binomial prior stabilizes these estimates by pulling them toward a league-wide baseline, reducing variance while preserving meaningful differences in well-sampled contexts. Rob Drake leads all active umpires with a shrinkage-adjusted miss rate of 9.4% and a regression effect of +0.156. At the other end, Edwin Jimenez (6.4%) and John Libka (6.4%) have the lowest miss rates among active umpires. The spread across this sample is approximately 3 percentage points in shrinkage rate, but the regression effects show a larger spread (−0.201 to +0.179) because they control for the context in which misses occur.

Table 4: Umpire miss rate rankings for 15 umpires active in 2026 . Shrinkage rate is the Beta-Binomial posterior mean with prior ($\alpha = 2, \beta = 20$). Regression effect is the umpire fixed effect from the L2-regularized logistic regression, controlling for pitch context. Positive regression effects indicate above-average miss tendency after controlling for context.

Umpire	n pitches	Raw miss rate	Shrinkage rate	Regression effect
Rob Drake	17,797	0.094	0.094	+0.156
CB Bucknor	22,521	0.093	0.093	+0.166
Laz Diaz	22,475	0.091	0.091	+0.123
Hunter Wendelstedt	17,962	0.091	0.091	+0.150
Ron Kulpa	15,878	0.089	0.089	+0.087
Doug Eddings	25,030	0.088	0.088	+0.029
Andy Fletcher	23,492	0.087	0.087	+0.140
Brian O’Nora	18,861	0.087	0.087	+0.052
Bruce Dreckman	19,656	0.085	0.085	+0.083
Malachi Moore	18,980	0.085	0.085	+0.095
Jeremie Rehak	22,524	0.066	0.066	-0.179
Alex Tosi	19,279	0.065	0.065	-0.201
John Libka	25,142	0.064	0.064	-0.147
Edwin Jimenez	9,476	0.064	0.064	-0.122

8.7 Expected CLS Heatmaps (Bayesian)

The expected CLS heatmap

$$E[\text{CLS}] = \text{CLS} \times P(\text{umpire misses in this direction})$$

is shown across the strike zone for three umpires (CB Bucknor, Edwin Jimenez, and Laz Diaz) under the reference game state: 3–2 count, tie game, 9th inning, 1 out, bases empty (Fig. 6). Each panel shows the spatial distribution of challenge value across the zone boundary, with the optimal challenge location (within 2.5 inches of the miss) marked by a filled dot. The gray contours show propensity boundaries.

CB Bucknor and Laz Diaz’s optimal challenge zone is low-outside for right-handed batters, consistent with the concentrated miss density shown in Fig. 6. Conversely, Edwin Jimenez has the optimal challenge zone high-inside. All three umpires return 100% $P(\text{challenge})$ at their best location, confirming that this high-leverage game state justifies using a challenge.

Figure 6: Expected CLS heat map for CB Bucknor, Edwin Jimenez, and Laz Diaz. $E[\text{CLS}] = \text{CLS} \times P(\text{umpire misses in this direction})$. 3-2, tie, inning 9, 1 out, bases empty. Gray contours show propensity boundaries. Filled dot marks the highest $E[\text{CLS}]$ location within 2.5 inches of miss. All three umpires show 100% $P(\text{challenge})$ at their optimal location, confirming the challenge value of this game state.

8.8 CLS by Batter Height (Bayesian)

The $E[\text{CLS}]$ heatmap is shown for CB Bucknor across three batter height bins (short: sz height 1.70 ft; average: 1.88 ft; tall: 2.06 ft) for right-handed batters against right-handed pitchers (Fig. 7). The directional miss rates vary across height bins, with high and inside miss rates decreasing as batter height increases (high: 0.110 to 0.062; inside: 0.115 to 0.084), while the low miss rate remains relatively stable (0.053 to 0.061). The outside miss rate remains the dominant component across all height bins, peaking for average-height batters (0.142). Consistent with this, the spatial concentration of elevated $E[\text{CLS}]$ along the outside-low boundary persists across all panels, indicating that CB Bucknor's low-pitch tendency is not materially attenuated by batter height.

Figure 7: $E[\text{CLS}]$ by batter height for CB Bucknor, RHB vs RHP. 3-2 called strike, tie game, inning 9, 1 out, bases empty. Shared color scale for direct comparison across height bins. Miss rates in the corner of each panel show how the directional propensities shift with batter height.

8.9 CLS by Batter and Pitcher Handedness (Bayesian)

The $E[\text{CLS}]$ heatmap is shown for CB Bucknor across all four handedness combinations (RHB vs RHP, RHB vs LHP, LHB vs RHP, LHB vs LHP) at average batter height (Fig. 8). All four panels use a shared color scale. The inside/outside miss directions flip for LHB against RHP and LHP, but not for RHB. This reflects that inside is a different physical location depending on batter stance but in this case only for LHB. The RHB vs LHP panel shows the highest outside miss rate (0.142), consistent with the arm-side/glove-side dynamics captured by the regression model.

Figure 8: $E[\text{CLS}]$ by batter and pitcher handedness for CB Bucknor, average batter height. 3-2 called strike, tie game, inning 9, 1 out, bases empty. Shared color scale. Inside/outside directions flip with batter handedness. RHB vs LHP shows the highest outside miss rate (0.142).

9 Implementation

The entire framework is implemented as an open-source Python toolkit and is available under a custom license. The repository is hosted at <https://github.com/butterflyology/challengeLeverageScore>. The codebase consists of seven modules (Table 5):

Table 5: The seven current modules present in the `challengeLeverageScore` repository.

Module	Description
<code>clsCoreFunctions.py</code>	CLS formula, <code>GameState</code> and <code>ChallengeContext</code> dataclasses, WE table builder
<code>clsBayesian.py</code>	Bayesian CLS with PyMC, contextual umpire lookup, credible interval reporting
<code>statCastPull.py</code>	Statcast data pipeline with per-season SHA-256 hash checkpointing
<code>umpirePull.py</code>	MLB Stats API umpire assignment pull and join
<code>umpireTendencies.py</code>	Beta-Binomial shrinkage model and logistic regression tendency model
<code>absDataPull.py</code>	ABS challenge outcome pipeline; pulls <code>reviewDetails</code> from MLB Stats API play-by-play endpoint and joins challenge outcomes to called pitch data
<code>incrementalPull.py</code>	In-season incremental data pipeline; pulls new called pitches, umpire assignments, and ABS challenge outcomes since the last pull date, with gap-check backfill for games missed by transient pull failures

The `challengeLeverageScore.ipynb` notebook can be used to reproduce the analyses, metrics, tables and figures presented in this document.

10 Discussion

10.1 Limitations

The current model has three calibration tiers. The win expectancy table is fully empirical, derived from six seasons of Statcast data and validated against published Tango values. The intercept β_0 is calibrated from 2026 ABS challenge outcomes. All other coefficients are development placeholders. This asymmetry means that game-state sensitivity (Figures 1 and 2) and miss distance sensitivity (Figure 3) are directionally correct and grounded in empirical data. Future versions of this project will address this by fitting all coefficients simultaneously from the growing corpus of pitch-level challenge outcomes, at which point Figures 7, 8, and 9 are expected to show meaningfully wider umpire spread.

A secondary limitation is that the WE table is built from called pitches only. This means that game states following balls in play are not directly observed and their WE is inferred from adjacent states. The use of `bat_win_exp` from Statcast mitigates this by providing the batting team's WE as computed by MLB from all pitch outcomes.

The framework does not model situations where the call is obviously wrong by a very large margin. These situations do not require a decision-support framework. However, teams will benefit from employing a disciplined approach to challenging pitches. The CLS is designed for the far more common case where the correct call is genuinely uncertain and the value of challenging must be weighed against the conservation cost.

10.2 Strategic Implications

Several strategic implications follow from the current framework. First, challenge value is highly concentrated in a small set of contexts, especially full-count called strikes in late, close games. Second, the conservation term materially suppresses early-game challenge use even when the immediate gain from overturning a call is positive. Third, the framework distinguishes between challenge value driven by count-state leverage and challenge value driven by umpire-specific miss tendencies, which are related but not interchangeable. In practice, disciplined teams should treat the framework as a way to reserve challenges for a narrow band of high-impact situations rather than as a license to challenge every close pitch.

10.3 Future Work

The most important next step is continued collection of pitch-level ABS challenge outcome data to fit the remaining overturn probability coefficients. Once fit, the overturn probability model should itself become a stochastic node in the Bayesian formulation, with a posterior over the coefficient vector. Additional planned extensions include a real-time game-state listener using the MLB Stats API live feed endpoint and a batter-specific lookup for unusual strike zones.

11 Conclusion

I have presented the Challenge Leverage Score, a decision-support framework for the MLB Automated Ball-Strike Challenge System. The framework formalizes the challenge decision as an expected-value problem and provides a practical implementation built on publicly available data. The intercept term has been calibrated from observed 2026 challenge outcomes, grounding absolute overturn probabilities in real data for the first time. The Bayesian extension enables uncertainty

quantification that accounts for the varying reliability of win expectancy estimates across game states and the varying precision of umpire tendency estimates across contexts.

The primary contribution is the formalization of the challenge conservation cost C_s , which approximates the dynamic programming value of retaining a challenge for future use. Most public discussion of when to challenge is imprecise about saving challenges for later. The CLS framework gives teams a principled, data-driven approach to this decision.

Ultimately the CLS is a tool for disciplined teams. Players cannot compute win expectancy differences in real time, but they can internalize the key qualitative findings: challenges are most valuable in late, close games on 3–2 calls; challenging called balls almost never benefits the batting team; and umpire identity genuinely matters. A team that understands these principles will make materially better challenge decisions than one relying on instinct alone.

Acknowledgements

Hearing announcer after announcer opine on challenge timing—and watching nearly all of them get it wrong—is what started this project. Only a few broadcast voices stood out as consistently coherent: Joe Davis and Orel Hersher as well as Stephen Nelson and Rick Monday. Upon hearing Jomboy remark that he believed a particular umpire systematically missed pitches to a specific zone against right-handed batters, I went straight to the literature. Several threads came together quickly: win expectancy, pitch framing research, and the structure of finite-resource decision problems. Training as an Evolutionary Ecologist and working professionally as a data scientist for a Consumer Packaged Goods company turns out to be reasonable preparation for this kind of work—I know how to ask a question, find the literature, and write the code. One intellectual debt stands above all others: Richard McElreath’s *Statistical Rethinking* reshaped how I think about uncertainty, and its influence runs through every Bayesian component of this framework. Nearly all of the writing, modeling, and coding took place at 36,000 feet across six Delta flights over the course of two weeks, and there is something genuinely satisfying about pushing `git` commits from cruise altitude. Company time played no role in this project whatsoever. Heeding the obvious disclosure requirement: no Nestlé resources of any kind were used in the creation of this work. Every opinion, modeling choice, and editorial decision is my own. Although this paper is not intended to be the final word on the subject, it is a beginning. That it came together in two weeks, mostly in the air, makes me prouder of it, not less. Engagement from anyone working on related problems is genuinely welcome. Doing this work was a pleasure.

References

- Brooks, D., Pavlidis, H., and Turkenkopf, D. (2013). Pitch framing and catcher effects. *Baseball Prospectus*.
- Carboch, J., Kocib, T., and S"uss, V. (2014). Analysis of hawk-eye challenges in tennis. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 32(16):1510–1518.
- Deshpande, S. K. and Wyner, A. J. (2017). A hierarchical bayesian model of pitch framing. *Journal of Quantitative Analysis in Sports*, 13(2):69–84.
- Fast, M. (2010). What the heck is pitch framing? *The Hardball Times*.
- Judge, T. A., Scott, B. A., and Ilies, R. (2010). Umpire bias in major league baseball: Evidence and implications. *Journal of Sport Management*, 24(3):281–303.

McElreath, R. (2020). *Statistical Rethinking: A Bayesian Course with Examples in R and Stan*. CRC Press, 2 edition.

Romer, D. (2006). Do firms maximize? evidence from professional football. *Journal of Political Economy*, 114(2):340–365.